

Scheme 1

with aromatic amines furnished 1-substituted-2-aryloxymethyl-4-(*p*-bis- β -cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-imidazolones (3) (Table 1). Ir spectra of both 2 and 3 showed bands at 1 590–1 600 (cyclic C=O) and 1 570–1 580 cm^{-1} (C=N).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF IMIDAZOLONES (3)*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour
$R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{H}$				
3a	H	107	57	Orange
b	$\text{CH}_3(o)$	127	42	Red
c	$\text{CH}_3(m)$	92	50	Brown
d	$\text{CH}_3(p)$	110	66	Orange
e	$\text{OCH}_3(o)$	136	44	Brown
f	$\text{OCH}_3(m)$	120	40	Brown
g	$\text{OCH}_3(p)$	142	60	Brown
h	$\text{Cl}(o)$	116	46	Pink
i	$\text{Cl}(m)$	100	52	Brown
j	$\text{Cl}(p)$	158	65	Orange
k	$\text{Br}(p)$	138	60	Red
l	$\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5(p)$	122	62	Orange
$R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{Cl}$				
3m	H	94	48	Orange
n	$\text{CH}_3(o)$	118	36	Black
o	$\text{CH}_3(m)$	104	42	Red
p	$\text{CH}_3(p)$	132	50	Brown
q	$\text{OCH}_3(p)$	126	55	Brown
r	$\text{Cl}(o)$	86	45	Red
s	$\text{Cl}(p)$	130	52	Brown
t	$\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5(p)$	112	60	Red

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Synthesis and Anti-HIV Activity of some New Imidazolones

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IMIDAZOLONES show wide range of pharmaceutical properties¹. In view of the effectiveness of drugs with cyanoethyl moiety², we report herein synthesis of some new 1-substituted-2-aryloxymethyl-4-(*p*-bis- β -cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-imidazolones (Scheme 1). Condensation of *p*-bis(β -cyanoethyl)aminobenzaldehyde with aryloxyacetylglycine (1) yielded 2-aryloxymethyl-4-(*p*-bis- β -cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolones (2). The latter on heating

Anti-HIV activity: The anti-HIV activity of compounds 3d, g, j, p and q were tested *in vitro* against infected treated culture and uninfected treated culture of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Maximum activity was found in case of 3p (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ANTI-HIV ACTIVITY OF IMIDAZOLONES (3)

Compd.	Dose	Infected response	Uninfected response
	M	Percent Control*	Percent Control*
3d	3.85×10^{-7}	17.22	104.71
g	8.54×10^{-9}	19.54	112.66
j	3.70×10^{-7}	16.10	98.83
p	1.58×10^{-4}	23.93	144.70
q	5.04×10^{-4}	19.06	109.08

*Control=AZT-treated culture under identical conditions.

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds 3 were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities using disc diffusion method³ at 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration against gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus*, *S. albus* and gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas pioseous*, and the fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* and *Alternaria alternata*.

Most of the compounds were found inactive against the fungi. 3l and 3t were moderately active against *S. aureus* and *S. albus* (12–14 mm, zone of inhibition).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

p-Bis(β -cyanoethyl)aminobenzaldehyde⁴ and phenoxyacetyl glycines⁵ were prepared by the reported methods.

2-Methylphenoxy-4-(*p*-bis(β -cyanoethylamino)benzylidene)-5-oxazolone (2a): A mixture of phenoxyacetyl glycine (0.01 mol), *p*-bis(β -cyanoethyl)aminobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (1 g) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) was heated on a flame for 5 min followed by heating on a steam-bath for 3 h when the contents solidified to a red mass. The solid was cooled and treated with cold aqueous ethanol (1 : 1), filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (42%), m.p. 117° (Found : C, 68.72; H, 4.89; N, 14.2. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 69.0; H, 5.0; N, 14.0%; ν_{max} 1595 (cyclic C=O), 1570 (C=N) and 810 cm^{-1} (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

2-(2',4'-Dichloromethylphenoxy)-4-(*p*-bis- β -cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolone (2b): It was prepared by aforementioned procedure using 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetyl glycine and *p*-bis(β -cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde), (67%), m.p. 156° (Found : C, 57.39; H, 3.62; N, 11.95; Cl, 15.23. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 58.72; H, 3.82; N, 11.91; Cl, 15.31%; ν_{max} 1600 (C=O), 1580 (C=N) and 820 cm^{-1} (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

1-Phenyl-2-methylphenoxy-4-(*p*-bis- β -cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-imidazolone (3a): A mixture of 2a (0.001 mol) and aniline (0.001 mol) were heated in an oil-bath at 160–70° for 2 h. The mass was then dissolved in hot ethanol and the contents were

poured on crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (57%), m.p. 107° (Found : C, 73.05; H, 5.21; N, 14.0. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 73.26; H, 5.26; N, 14.73%; ν_{max} 1600 (C=O), 1570 (C=N) and 810 cm^{-1} (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

Other imidazolones (3b–t) were synthesised similarly.

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